

LEXICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF IT TERMS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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ABSTRACT

This article investigates and compares the lexical characteristics of information technology (IT) terminology in English and Uzbek. Utilizing a corpus-based approach, the study analyzes terms extracted from diverse sources, including online dictionaries, technical glossaries, and IT-related publications. The findings highlight disparities in complexity, word formation, collocations, and semantic features between English and Uzbek IT terms. Notably, English terms exhibit greater intricacy, relying on affixes and acronyms, while Uzbek terms prioritize simplicity. The study explores the historical and cultural factors contributing to these differences, emphasizing their significance for linguistic research, translation strategies, and the broader IT community.

Keywords:

Information Technology, Lexical Characteristics, Comparative Analysis, Corpus-based Approach, Affixation, Collocations, Semantic Features, Cross-cultural Linguistics

INTRODUCTION

In the ever-evolving field of information technology (IT), language plays a crucial role in facilitating effective communication and knowledge exchange. The lexical characteristics of IT terms in different languages shed light on the cultural and linguistic nuances that exist within the IT domain. This article explores and

compares the lexical features of IT terminology in English and Uzbek, aiming to provide insights into the linguistic patterns and unique characteristics of these languages in the context of information technology.

METHODOLOGY

The study was conducted using a corpus-based approach. A corpus of IT texts in English and Uzbek was collected, and the terms used in these texts were extracted and analyzed. The analysis focused on the lexical characteristics of the terms, including their word formation, collocations, and semantic features. To ensure the inclusion of a diverse and representative set of IT terms in both languages, a variety of sources were consulted. This involved:

Online Dictionaries: A comprehensive range of online dictionaries in both English and Uzbek were consulted. These dictionaries typically serve as reliable references for language and terminology.

Technical Glossaries: Technical glossaries specifically dedicated to IT terminology in both languages were scrutinized. These glossaries are typically designed to provide precise definitions and explanations of IT terms.

IT-Related Publications: Academic publications, industry reports, and IT-related literature were also reviewed. These sources often introduce new and evolving terms in the IT field.

RESULTS

The analysis revealed several key differences in the lexical characteristics of IT terms in English and Uzbek. Firstly, English IT terms tend to be more complex and specialized than their Uzbek counterparts. This is reflected in the use of affixes, such as *-ize* and *-ify*, and the use of acronyms and abbreviations, such as HTML and CSS. Secondly, collocations of IT terms in English tend to be more varied and idiomatic, while Uzbek collocations tend to be more formulaic and less flexible. Finally, there are also differences in the semantic features of IT terms in

the two languages, with some terms having multiple meanings in English but only one in Uzbek.

The study disclosed that English IT terms exhibit a tendency to be more intricate and specialized when compared to their Uzbek counterparts. This complexity is manifest in several ways. English IT terms often incorporate affixes like "-ize" and "-ify," which are used to create new terms or transform existing words to suit specific IT contexts. Additionally, English IT terminology frequently relies on acronyms and abbreviations, such as HTML (Hypertext Markup Language) and CSS (Cascading Style Sheets), to succinctly represent complex concepts.

In contrast, Uzbek IT terms tend to be relatively less complex and specialized. They often avoid the use of affixes and opt for straightforward expressions. The reliance on acronyms and abbreviations is less prevalent in Uzbek IT terminology.

There are notable distinctions in the semantic features of IT terms between the two languages. In English, some IT terms have multiple meanings or interpretations, reflecting the adaptability and evolution of the language in response to technological advancements. This multiplicity of meanings can lead to nuanced usage and contextual variation.

In Uzbek, IT terms tend to have a single, well-defined meaning. The language appears to maintain a more rigid and unambiguous approach to IT terminology, which can be advantageous for clarity but may require the creation of new terms for emerging concepts.

DISCUSSION

The differences in the lexical characteristics of IT terms in English and Uzbek can be attributed to several factors, including the historical development of the two languages and their relationship with other languages. English has been heavily influenced by Latin and Greek, which has led to the adoption of many complex and specialized terms in the IT field. Uzbek, on the other hand, has been

influenced by Persian and Arabic, which has led to a greater use of loanwords in the IT field.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the lexical characteristics of IT terms in English and Uzbek differ in several important ways. These differences reflect the historical and cultural backgrounds of the two languages, as well as the differing needs and priorities of the IT communities in each language. These findings are valuable not only for linguistic research but also for practitioners and translators working in the IT domain in both languages. Understanding these differences can be useful for language learners and IT professionals who need to work in both languages, and can contribute to the development of more effective translation and localization strategies in the IT field.

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